

Gravimetric Determination of Gold using Oxalic Acid an Improved Procedure

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A modified procedure for the gravimetric determination of gold using oxalic acid has been developed. Quantities ranging from 10-100 mg. of gold could be accurately determined. Precipitation from homogeneous solutions using ethyl oxalate was described and the advantages pointed out. The easy reduction of gold was explained. The method developed was applied for the determination of gold in commercial samples.

GOLD was estimated using oxalic acid as a reagent^{1,2}. The precipitation was carried out in an acid medium. The procedure needed digestion for long hours (over night) over hot water bath and the precipitate obtained was exceedingly fine. We have now found that gold could be conveniently precipitated in an hours' time by adopting the following procedure using the same reagent, oxalic acid. The procedure yielded a comparatively better form of precipitate, thus facilitating easier filtration and needing less manipulative care.

Experimental

The gold used in the investigation was obtained from the local market and was purified by adopting the procedure developed by Paul Drawe³. The purified gold was dissolved in aquaregia and carefully evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid and the acid strength adjusted to 0.1N. The solution contained about 1 mg of gold per ml and was standardised gravimetrically using hydroquinone⁴. A separate gold solution of about the same strength was also prepared using chloroauric acid supplied by Johnson-Mathey Co., London and standardised gravimetrically⁴. Both the solutions were utilised in our investigations.

Recommended Procedure

A known volume of the standard gold solution was pipetted out into a clean beaker (150 ml.). A 1N solution of potassium hydroxide (A.R.) was next added dropwise with stirring until the yellow colour was just discharged and a further amount of 2 ml. was added. The solution was diluted to ca. 75 ml. with distilled water. 5-6 ml. of 1N oxalic acid solution were then added dropwise with stirring and the contents were kept on a boiling water bath. Within a few minutes the solution turned purple with a violet tinge and soon gold separated out. The beaker was kept on the water bath for about an hour with occasional stirring. The solution was filtered through a Whatman No. 42 (7 cms) filter

paper. Small particles sticking to the beaker were transferred into the filter by use of small pieces of high grade filter paper. The precipitate was washed with about 75 ml. of distilled water, dried and ignited in a silica crucible and weighed as metal. The results recorded in table 1 clearly show that this method could be employed with advantage for the gravimetric determination of gold.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF GOLD USING OXALIC ACID

S.No.	Gold (mg.)		Error %
	Taken	Found	
1.	9.08	9.00	-0.66
2.	13.60	13.70	+0.74
3.	18.12	18.10	-0.11
4.	22.15	22.20	+0.23
5.	45.30	45.40	+0.22
6.	67.95	67.70	-0.37
7.	90.60	90.00	-0.66

Experiments were also carried out using ethyl oxalate for precipitation from homogeneous solutions. The procedure adopted was the same as described above except for the addition of 2-3 ml. of ethyl oxalate in place of oxalic acid. The results obtained are given in table 2. We recommend ethyl oxalate as a precipitant because gold obtained was still in a much better form permitting easier transfer and filtration.

TABLE 2—PRECIPITATION OF GOLD FROM HOMOGENEOUS SOLUTIONS USING ETHYL OXALATE

S.No.	Gold (mg.)		Error %
	Taken	Found	
1.	9.06	9.02	-0.44
2.	13.60	13.60	0.00
3.	18.12	18.20	+0.44
4.	22.15	22.10	-0.23
5.	45.30	45.30	0.00
6.	67.95	67.90	-0.074
7.	90.60	90.30	-0.33

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF GOLD IN COMMERCIAL SAMPLES

S.No.	Gold taken (mg)	Added		Gold found (mg)	Error %
		copper (mg)	iron (mg)		
1.	33.4	12.0	—	33.55	+0.45
2.	33.4	—	15.0	33.60	+0.60
3.	33.4	10.0	10.0	33.50	+0.30
4.	33.4	16.0	20.0	33.10	-0.90
5.	41.7	15.0	—	41.90	+0.48
6.	41.7	—	10.0	41.60	-0.24
7.	41.7	15.0	15.0	41.50	-0.48
8.	41.7	17.0	10.0	41.80	+0.24
9.	66.8	15.0	15.0	66.60	-0.30

Discussion

The interesting observation that oxalic acid could reduce gold quantitatively from the alkaline solution more easily and in a shorter time than in acid medium may be explained on the following lines :

Oxalic acid first neutralises the excess alkali. AuO_2^- which is present in the solution is converted to $\text{Au}(\text{OH})_3$

The $\text{Au}(\text{OH})_3$ produced is reduced by oxalic acid to gold.

We prepared auric hydroxide by adding a requisite amount of potassium hydroxide to the gold chloride solution. The precipitated auric hydroxide was taken in two different test tubes. To one oxalic acid was directly added. To the other, dilute solution of hydrochloric acid was added just enough to dissolve the precipitate, followed by oxalic acid. Both the test tubes were then heated on a water bath. In the former case, the precipitation was found to take

place in a few seconds while in the latter it took a few minutes. These observations lend support to the mechanism suggested.

Determination of Gold in Commercial Samples

With a view to estimate gold in commercial samples, which contains small amounts of iron and copper, a procedure has been developed.

Procedure

Copper and iron in small amounts were added to the gold solution. A 1N solution of potassium hydroxide was added dropwise with stirring until the precipitation was complete and 2 ml. of the alkali were further added. The precipitate was allowed to settle and then filtered through a Whatman No. 41 filter paper, washed with about 20 ml. of 1% solution of potassium hydroxide and then with distilled water until the filtrate collected was about 100 ml. Gold from the filtrate was estimated adopting the procedure given above. The results obtained are recorded in Table 3.

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